

OPINIONS OF RESIDENTS OF NKANU EAST LGA ON THE ROLES OF THE INTERNET IN SOCIOCULTURAL HOMOGENISATION

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between Internet usage and contemporary sociocultural identities among rural residents of Nkanu East Local Government Area (LGA) in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design and utilised a structured questionnaire and an interview guide as instruments of data collection. A sample of 399 respondents was drawn from a projected 2023 population of 237,145 residents, using the Taro Yamane sampling formula. Purposive and random sampling techniques were employed. Quantitative data were analysed using frequency distribution tables and simple percentages, while qualitative data from interview sessions were thematically coded and integrated into the discussion. The study found that the majority of respondents acknowledged a high association between their consumption of Internet contents and shifts in their sociocultural behaviours. Residents were found to be substantially exposed to Internet contents, primarily through smart mobile phones and digitised television, using platforms such as WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, and television channels. Almost all domains of the people's primordial cultural life, including fashion, language, religion, politics, and commerce, have been affected to varying degrees, exhibiting either homogenised or hybridised characteristics. The study concludes that the Internet serves as a principal driver of sociocultural homogenisation even in rural settings, and recommends coordinated governmental and institutional action to preserve indigenous cultural identities through localised policy, community media, and education.

Keywords: Internet, sociocultural homogenisation, rural communities, Nkanu East, cultural hybridisation, Nigeria

Introduction

The proliferation of Internet-enabled devices and the increasing penetration of digital media into rural communities have intensified scholarly interest in the relationship between new communication technologies and sociocultural change. In Nigeria, where approximately 122 million people (slightly above half the total population) were registered as active Internet users as at 2023 (Statista Research Department, 2022), the transformative potential of online content reaches well beyond urban centres. Of Nigeria's estimated 2023 population of 223,804,632, approximately 45.4% reside in rural areas (Macrotrends, 2024), raising important questions about the extent to which digital media reshapes cultural life in communities historically characterised by limited infrastructure.

These days, media outfits across conventional and social media platforms disseminate pieces of information about segments of the present generation of the Igbo nation behaving in manners socially and culturally alien to the people's established values, norms, and mores. In the core tradition of the Nkanu East people, certain practices and value systems that now permeate the community are historically foreign. Yet, these behaviours appear widely in local settings. The question this study raises is: what has driven this cultural shift in communities that are largely insulated from the direct physical influence of foreign climes?

According to ITPulse (2021), experts at the Worldwide Web Day Conference held in Lagos argued that ubiquitous and affordable Internet would facilitate greater Nigerian participation in the digital economy.

Meanwhile, the president of the Institute of Software Practitioners of Nigeria (IPSON) noted that ubiquitous Internet connectivity would enhance digital transformation and national development (Mba-Uzoukwu, 2021). These perspectives reflect the instrumental case for Internet expansion; however, they largely ignore the sociocultural ramifications of such connectivity, particularly in communities with deeply embedded traditional identities.

Existing scholarship is divided on the matter. A first school of thought maintains that the Internet has permeated every nook and cranny of the globe, including rural localities, driving sociocultural, commercial, economic, and political homogenisation (Unwana, 2020; Nwaolikpe, 2020; Onoja et al., 2020; Obayi et al., 2020; Olukotun et al., 2013). A second school asserts that infrastructure deficits in rural areas render Internet influence relatively ineffective, creating what has been described as a digital blackout for rural dwellers (Emejulu, 2004; Eze, 2007; Sambe, 2007). This study is an empirical attempt to resolve this tension by surveying the opinions of residents of three of the remotest communities of Nkanu East LGA: Amagunze, Ihuokpara, and Nkerefi.

Statement of the Problem

A number of assertions have been made about what the Internet has done, through its associated technologies, in influencing people's values, norms, and behaviours in favour of dominant Western cultures. Some researchers have argued that such influences are negligible in rural settings due to inadequate infrastructure. This study, therefore, sets out to conduct an empirical survey to evaluate the veracity of claims about a wide urban-rural digital divide, particularly as it pertains to Internet-driven sociocultural change among rural residents of Nkanu East LGA, Enugu State.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study was to evaluate the opinions of rural dwellers in Nkanu East LGA on the association between their use of the Internet and observable shifts in their contemporary sociocultural behaviours. The specific objectives were to:

1. Determine the extent of association between the new sociocultural behaviours of Nkanu East residents and their consumption of Internet contents.
2. Evaluate the extent to which rural residents of Nkanu East expose themselves to different Internet contents.
3. Determine the Internet contents that Nkanu East residents are most exposed to.
4. Ascertain the Internet technologies most used by Nkanu East residents.
5. Identify the Internet channels used most by Nkanu East residents.
6. Evaluate the cultural elements of Nkanu East residents most impacted by Internet exposure.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of association between the new sociocultural behaviours of Nkanu East residents and their consumption of Internet contents?
2. To what extent do rural residents of Nkanu East expose themselves to different Internet contents?
3. What Internet contents are Nkanu East residents most exposed to?
4. Which Internet technologies do Nkanu East residents use most?
5. Which Internet channels do Nkanu East residents use most?
6. Which cultural elements of Nkanu East residents have been most impacted by Internet exposure?

Significance of the Study

This study contributes to the growing body of literature on Internet use and cultural change in rural Nigeria. Its findings have implications for communication scholars, policymakers, rural development agencies, cultural institutions, and marketers targeting rural demographics. By providing empirical evidence of Internet influence on sociocultural life in one of Nigeria's remotest rural local governments, the study challenges infrastructure-deficit arguments and offers nuanced insights into digital penetration in non-urban communities. The study will be made accessible through online repositories, institutional libraries, and academic databases.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to three contiguous and culturally consanguineous communities of Nkanu East LGA in Enugu East Senatorial District of Enugu State: Amaganze, Ihuokpara, and Nkerefi. These communities were selected for their shared cultural identity, their status as boundary communities between Enugu and Ebonyi States, and their classification as areas with limited urban infrastructure. The study does not extend to urban communities, where Internet infrastructure is relatively more developed.

Operational Definition of Terms

In the context of this study and in accordance with established definitional conventions (Nwodu, 2006; Osuala, 1982; Babbie, 2010), certain terms are defined as follows:

Cultural Elements: The essential principles, norms, values, and practices that are distinctively characteristic of the Nkanu East people and by which they are differentiated from neighbouring communities.

Homogenisation: The process by which Nkanu East residents, previously distinct from and largely ignorant of other sociocultural identities, are increasingly coming to exhibit similar cultural outlooks and behaviours to those of other communities.

Internet Channels: Social media platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, Twitter (now X), WhatsApp, and YouTube, through which Nkanu East residents are exposed to content that has the capacity to influence their opinions, values, and behaviours.

Internet Contents: Sociocultural texts, images, films, videos, and audio-visual materials consumed through the Internet that have the potential to influence the values, norms, and behaviours of Nkanu East residents.

Internet Technologies: The devices that enable Internet access, including desktop and laptop computers, smart mobile phones, and digitised and digitalised television sets.

Sociocultural Identity: The values, norms, mores, and cultural practices by which the Nkanu East LGA community may be distinctively identified and compared with other communities.

Review of Related Literature

The literature review in this study is thematic, theoretical, and empirical. The thematic review examines concepts central to the study; the theoretical review critically analyses the theories on which the study is anchored; and the empirical review surveys relevant prior studies. Sources include peer-reviewed journals, books, edited book chapters, theses, and online publications.

The Internet in Nigeria

The history of the Internet in Nigeria dates to approximately 1986, with effective full access commencing in 1998 (Adomi, 2005). According to reports retrieved by Vanguard (2010), the Internet arrived in Nigeria seven years after its introduction in the United States of America. In 1996, the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) licensed 38 Internet Service Providers (ISPs), and on 1 January 1997, Linkserve Limited commenced commercial operations as the country's first ISP. By 2003, the NCC had licensed over 150 ISPs (Adomi, 2005; Vladica, 2017).

Agba (2002) defines the Internet as a multimedia information superhighway that facilitates businesses, sports, politics, entertainment, and other endeavours across international boundaries. Ogbuoshi (2005) describes it as a network of computers communicating through a common language designed to enable systems of different manufacturers at different locations anywhere in the world to exchange data and information. The Internet, as noted by Dominick (2002, p. 20), has brought computers into the realm of mass communication, reversing the established pattern of one-to-many communication and creating a new category of mass communicators.

Sambe and Utoh (2014) note that from the 1950s onwards, communication infrastructure underwent rapid expansion, witnessing the proliferation of domestic information and communication technologies (ICTs) such as telephones, radios, and televisions. Nwanwene (2017) identifies ICTs as technologies that can be combined to facilitate communication, processing, and transmission of information by electronic means. By 2023, approximately 122 million Nigerians were registered as active Internet users, representing slightly above half of Nigeria's projected population (Statista Research Department, 2022).

Homogenisation and Internet Technologies

For the purposes of this study, homogenisation refers to the process by which people previously distinct in values, norms, mores, origins, and identities come to present uniformity in their contemporary sociocultural identities. Cultural homogenisation has been described as an aspect of cultural globalisation characterised by a reduction in cultural diversity through the diffusion of cultural symbols, customs, ideas, values, and norms (Google Arts and Culture, n.d.). As Adamu (2006) observed, the transmission of cultural activities across societies was historically facilitated by migration and literacy; however, contemporary mass media, particularly Internet-mediated content, has become a far more pervasive and rapid vector for cross-cultural influence.

Adamu (2006) documented that in northern Nigeria, continuous broadcast of foreign media cultures, particularly Indian Hindu films, had, by 2006, so permeated the popular Hausa culture that the Hindu film music template was adopted by major marketing companies in the region. This study noted a corresponding decline in the patronage of Hausa traditional musicians, illustrating how media-driven cultural influx can displace indigenous cultural forms.

MacBride et al. (1981, pp. 159–160) observed that the rapid increase in the volume of information and entertainment has produced a degree of societal homogenisation. They noted, paradoxically, that people can become more alienated from their immediate societies as a result of media penetration. Conversi (2010) affirms that cultural homogenisation often aims to achieve congruence between ethnic and political boundaries, functioning as a state-led policy of cultural standardisation. More broadly, the Internet functions as the channel through which local cultures are absorbed or hybridised by cultures previously alien to the people (Grosswiler, 2011).

Kraid (2004) argued that cultural globalisation in the latter half of the twentieth century became increasingly synonymous with cultural Americanisation, with American popular culture, including Hollywood films, fast food, sportswear, music television, and teenage fashion, was reaching even the most remote parts of the world. This resonates with the observable reality in Nkanu East communities, where dressing patterns, entertainment preferences, and even language use increasingly reflect global, Western-inflected cultural norms.

Sociocultural Homogenisation

How does homogenisation occur between communities previously ignorant of one another's existence? Bittner (1989, p. 337) describes the powerful influence of international communication and inter-cultural exchange across international boundaries, noting that people of different cultural backgrounds can easily

become uniform in many of their sociocultural practices. Kim et al. (2009) argue that the Internet has become a hybridised space in which individuals can manage complex interactions between their home and host cultures without necessarily dissolving either.

Eluwa et al. (2014) reveal that the Internet has improved economic activities and facilitated better relationships among people of different ethnic backgrounds. Alexmoore (2002) posits that the growth of the Internet has allowed for greater communication and interaction between people of different cultural backgrounds. Onwuamalam (2005) observes that the use of hybrid linguistic forms such as 'Engligbo', a blend of English and Igbo, in broadcast programmes smacks of cultural homogenisation, which risks bastardising the essence of language in communication.

MacBride et al. (1981) warned that too often, the benefits of modern communication, namely vivid and absorbing information and entertainment originating from urban centres and frequently from foreign sources, have been accompanied by negative influences that can dramatically disturb established cultural orders. At the extreme, modern media have trampled on traditions and distorted centuries-old socio-economic patterns (MacBride et al., 1981).

Theoretical Framework

Technological Determinism Theory

This study is partly anchored on Technological Determinism theory, first attributed to Thorstein Veblen (1857–1929), an American sociologist and economist. The theory posits that a society's technology is the primary driver of its sociocultural structures and values (Chukwu, 2015). It conceptualises technical development, media, and technology as the key mover in social history and change. Technological Determinism is particularly relevant to this study because the ubiquitous availability of the Internet as a media technology affords rural residents the opportunity to interact with other cultural contexts seamlessly. Through Internet-enabled devices, individuals can navigate global cultural spaces from within their homes, gradually acculturating sociocultural elements previously alien to them.

However, it is important to note that Technological Determinism has been critiqued for overemphasising the agency of technology while underemphasising human choice and social context (Williams, 1974). This study does not subscribe to a purely determinist position; rather, it regards Internet technology as a powerful enabling factor whose effects are mediated by patterns of use, access, and motivation.

Uses and Gratification Theory

The Uses and Gratification theory, first propounded in 1974 by Elihu Katz, Jay Blumler, and Michael Gurevitch (Nwaolikpe, 2020), provides the second theoretical anchor for this study. The theory emphasises the active role of media consumers in selecting media content to satisfy specific needs. Rather than asking what media does to audiences, it asks who uses which content, for which reasons, and with what effects (Okunna & Omenugha, 2012, in Unwana, 2020). McQuail (2005, p. 423) posits that media use depends on perceived satisfaction, needs, wishes, or motives of audience members.

In the context of this study, Uses and Gratification theory explains why rural residents of Nkanu East actively seek out and consume specific Internet contents, such as sociocultural films, political updates, religious programming, and fashion content, as a means of satisfying particular sociocultural needs. The gratification derived from such content reinforces continued consumption and gradually reshapes the consumers' cultural orientations. Together, Technological Determinism and Uses and Gratification theories account for both the enabling infrastructure of the Internet and the purposive behaviour of the audience in using it, forming a coherent theoretical frame for understanding Internet-driven homogenisation in rural communities.

Review of Empirical Studies

Unwana (2020) examined the impact of transnational broadcasting of European football leagues on elite local leagues. The study involved a population of 36 sports journalists across Nigeria's 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory, with a sample of 19 journalists. Using a qualitative research design with in-depth interview guides, the study found multiple effects, including declining viewership of local free-to-air television, increasing migration of African footballers to Europe and Asia, and a decline in stadium spectatorship as fans relocated to bars and restaurants to watch European football.

Nwaolikpe (2020) surveyed the influence of cyberbullying on the academic, social, and emotional well-being of undergraduates of Caleb University, Imota-Lagos. Using a mixed-methods design with a population of 2,508 students and a sample of 300, the study found that undergraduates experienced significant academic, social, and emotional challenges due to cyberbullying.

Onoja et al. (2020) conducted a historical evaluation of social media use in Nigeria's presidential elections from 2007 to 2019. The study found that social media had deepened the electioneering process, raised citizens' participation in political processes, and served both positive and negative functions, including the spread of fake news and hate speech.

Obayi et al. (2020), anchored on cultivation theory, examined the influence of violent cartoon films on children in Aba metropolis. Using a survey design with 384 respondents drawn from a population of 1,081,466, the study found that approximately 52% of children were exposed to violent cartoon scenes and that approximately 72% of those who watched violent cartoons exhibited behavioural changes.

Olukotun et al. (2013) studied the introduction of GSM services in Anyigba community and its impact on students' expenditure patterns. Using a survey with 300 respondents, the study found a significant relationship between mobile phone usage and student expenditure patterns, with students increasingly prioritising airtime over cash.

Ifejika et al. (2009) examined the use of mobile phones in fish-selling businesses, using a multi-stage sampling technique with 60 respondents. The study found that mobile phones had become a useful channel for fish sellers to reach customers and suppliers in real time, representing a significant paradigm shift from traditional fish-selling practices.

Arijeniwa et al. (2022) conducted a conceptual and empirical assessment of the impact of social media on the promotion of synthetic values in Nigeria, published in *Discourses on Communication and Media Studies in Contemporary Society*. The study argued that the Internet, through social media, has efficiently aided the rise of globalisation through its audio-visual advantages, which have transcended the barriers of time and space associated with traditional media. The study found that cultural commodification via social media had deeply penetrated Nigerian society, especially among youth, and was significantly eroding indigenous cultural values and heritage. The researchers recommended that Nigerians, particularly the youth, be reoriented to actively project their own cultural heritage through the same social media platforms rather than passively absorbing foreign values.

Balogun and Aruoture (2024) examined the dual role of social media in cultural homogenisation and cultural diversity, presenting it as a double-edged sword, in a study published in the *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*. The study found that social media facilitates the rapid dissemination of predominantly Western global cultural trends, leading to the erosion of local traditions, languages, and identities among African youth. The researchers observed that African youth increasingly adopt global consumer behaviours, fashion, and entertainment, often at the expense of indigenous cultural practices. At the same time, the study found that social media also offers opportunities for cultural diversity and the preservation of indigenous identity when consciously deployed for that purpose. The study's findings are

directly relevant to the Nkanu East context, where this study similarly observed pervasive Western cultural influence across multiple domains of social life.

Uwalaka and Nwala (2023) examined the role of social media and mobile social networking applications in socio-political contestations in Nigeria, published in *Communication and the Public*. Using data collected during the 2020 #EndSARS protests in Nigeria, the study found that social media and mobile applications played significant roles in organising, planning, and documenting the protests. The study demonstrated that digital platforms have substantially transformed political participation in Nigeria, enabling citizens to mobilise around shared socio-political concerns in ways previously impossible. These findings are consistent with the present study's observation that rural residents of Nkanu East actively used Internet platforms to monitor vote collation and engage in political discourse during the 2019 and 2023 general elections.

Summary of Literature Reviewed

The literature reviewed demonstrates that the Internet has permeated Nigerian society at multiple levels and across demographic categories. While some scholars argued that infrastructure deficits restricted Internet influence in rural areas (Emejulu, 2004; Eze, 2007; Sambe, 2007), a growing body of empirical evidence suggests that smart mobile phones and digitised television have effectively bridged much of this gap (Unwana, 2020; Nwaolikpe, 2020; Onoja et al., 2020; Arijenwa et al., 2022; Balogun & Aruoture, 2024). The reviewed studies confirm that the Internet drives sociocultural change, economic transformation, and political participation in both urban and rural contexts. Balogun and Aruoture (2024) specifically document that among African youth, the adoption of foreign cultural norms through social media is increasingly displacing indigenous practices, a finding that aligns directly with the observations made in Nkanu East. Uwalaka and Nwala (2023) further demonstrate that mobile social networking platforms have transformed political participation in Nigeria. However, few studies have focused specifically on the sociocultural implications of Internet use in the remotest communities of southeastern Nigeria, representing the empirical gap this study addresses.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Survey research design is appropriate when collecting data skewed towards interpreting existing conditions, events, or attitudes within a defined population (Nworgu, 1991, pp. 58–59; Ogbuoshi, 2006, p. 145). The descriptive survey design was deemed suitable for this study because the primary objective was not to establish experimental causation but to document respondents' opinions about observed changes in their sociocultural lives and the factors they associate with those changes. The study supplements quantitative survey data with qualitative data collected through structured interviews, thereby enabling a richer interpretation of findings. This mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative frequency analysis with qualitative thematic reporting, is consistent with convergent parallel mixed-methods design (Creswell, 2014).

Population

The population for this study comprised all residents of Nkanu East LGA as at the end of 2023. Using the standard formula for population projection (Owuamalam, 2012, p. 107), the 2006 census figure of 153,591 (Federal Government Printers, 2009) was projected over 17 years at Nigeria's standard population growth rate of 3.2% per annum, yielding a projected population of approximately 237,145.

The population projection formula is as follows:

$$PP = GP + (GP \times Pi \times T)$$

Where: PP = Population Projection; GP = Given Population (as at last census); Pi = Population growth index (3.2% = 0.032); T = Time in years between census year and study year.
Thus: $PP = 153,591 + (153,591 \times 0.032 \times 17) = 153,591 + 83,553 = 237,144 \approx 237,145$

Sample Size

Using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula as cited in Ogbuoshi (2006, p. 85), a sample of 399 was drawn from the projected population of 237,145 at a 5% level of significance:
 $n = N / [1 + N(e)^2] = 237,145 / [1 + (237,145 \times 0.0025)] = 237,145 / 594.36 \approx 399$
The sample size of 399 was considered representative of the population, given the homogeneity of the rural LGA and the precision desired.

Sampling Technique

The researcher employed purposive and random sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used to select the three contiguous remotest communities of Nkanu East LGA: Amagunze (133 respondents), Ihuokpara (133 respondents), and Nkerefi (133 respondents). These communities were selected because they share cultural consanguinity, possess the defining characteristics of rural areas, occupy the boundary zone between Enugu and Ebonyi States, and are among the most infrastructure-deficient communities in the LGA. Random sampling was used in each community, with questionnaires administered to respondents selected randomly at community market squares, ensuring that all categories of residents had an equal probability of selection.

Instruments for Data Collection

The study employed two instruments: a structured questionnaire for quantitative data collection and an interview guide for qualitative data collection. The questionnaire contained two sections. Section A collected demographic data, including age, educational level, and length of residence in Nkanu East LGA. Section B contained items structured on a five-point Likert scale: Higher Extent, High Extent, Not Sure, Low Extent, and Lower Extent. These items elicited respondents' opinions on the relationship between Internet consumption and shifts in their sociocultural behaviours, their preferred Internet technologies and channels, the types of content most consumed, and the cultural domains most affected.

The structured interview guide was used to collect qualitative data on respondents' motivations, subjective experiences, and contextual explanations for the cultural changes they acknowledged. Data from both instruments were used in a complementary manner to provide depth to the quantitative findings.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The measuring instruments were subjected to face and content validation by two experts in the Department of Mass Communication, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, in accordance with standard validation procedures (Asika, 2006, p. 71; Gravetter & Forzano, 2009, p. 157). Their observations and corrections were incorporated before fieldwork commenced. This process ensured that the instruments measured what they were designed to measure and that the items adequately covered the scope and objectives of the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data collected through the questionnaire were analysed using frequency distribution tables and simple percentages. These descriptive statistics were used to summarise respondents' opinions on each of the research questions. Given the ordinal nature of the Likert-scale data and the descriptive-survey design adopted, frequency and percentage analysis was appropriate for the study's purposes. Qualitative data from the interview guide were analysed thematically, with emerging themes coded and integrated into the discussion of findings to enrich the quantitative results.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The tables below present the distribution of respondents' opinions on each of the six research questions. Frequencies and simple percentages are reported for each item.

Table 1: Extent of Association Between New Sociocultural Behaviours and Internet Content Consumption

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Higher Extent	40	10.0%
High Extent	203	50.9%
Not Sure	56	14.0%
Low Extent	32	8.0%
Lower Extent	68	17.0%
Total	399	100%

Table 1 shows that a combined 60.9% of respondents indicated that there is a high or higher-extent association between their new sociocultural behaviours and their consumption of Internet contents, while only 25% reported a low or lower-extent relationship. These findings suggest that the majority of Nkanu East residents perceive a meaningful link between their Internet use and observable changes in their cultural attitudes and behaviours.

Table 2: Extent of Exposure to Internet Contents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Higher Extent	36	9.0%
High Extent	207	51.9%
Not Sure	56	14.0%
Low Extent	48	12.0%
Lower Extent	52	13.0%
Total	399	100%

Table 2 indicates that 60.9% of respondents reported exposing themselves to Internet contents at high or higher extent, while 25% reported low or lower exposure. This finding challenges earlier assertions that rural infrastructure deficits effectively limit Internet access and use among rural Nigerians (Emejulu, 2004; Samba, 2007).

Table 3: Internet Contents Most Consumed by Nkanu East Residents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Sports	60	15.0%
Lifestyle/Fashion Features	55	13.8%
Sociocultural/Religious Movies	203	50.9%
Political Content	57	14.3%
Educational Content	24	6.0%
Total	399	100%

Table 3 reveals that sociocultural and religious movies constitute the most consumed category of Internet content among Nkanu East residents (50.9%), followed by sports (15.0%) and political content (14.3%). This suggests that the primary vector of cultural influence in these communities is demonstrative, audio-visual media content rather than text-based or educational material.

Table 4: Internet Technologies Most Used by Nkanu East Residents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
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Radio	29	7.3%
Desktop/Laptop Computers	40	10.0%
Smart Mobile Phones	181	45.4%
Digitised/Digitalised TVs	149	37.3%
Any Other	0	0%
Total	399	100%

Table 4 shows that smart mobile phones are the dominant Internet-access technology among Nkanu East residents (45.4%), followed closely by digitised and digitalised television sets (37.3%). This finding is notable given the rural setting of the study, as it indicates a level of technological penetration that contradicts the infrastructure-deficit narrative.

Table 5: Internet Channels Most Used by Nkanu East Residents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Facebook/Messenger	92	23.1%
Instagram/Twitter (X)	20	5.0%
WhatsApp/YouTube	118	29.6%
Television/Teleporting	154	38.6%
Local Role Models	15	3.8%
Total	399	100%

Table 5 indicates that television and teleporting (38.6%) and WhatsApp/YouTube (29.6%) are the most widely used channels for Internet content consumption. Social media platforms such as Facebook and WhatsApp together account for over 52% of online activity, underscoring their significant role as vectors of cultural influence.

Table 6: Cultural Elements of Nkanu East Most Impacted by Internet Exposure

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Language	20	5.0%
Fashion	55	13.8%
Music	10	2.5%
Commerce	22	5.5%
Education	35	8.8%
Sports	41	10.3%
Food/Agriculture	36	9.0%
Religion	47	11.8%
Politics	63	15.8%
News/Information	59	14.8%
Building Styles	11	2.7%
Total	399	100%

Table 6 reveals that politics (15.8%), news and information (14.8%), and fashion (13.8%) are the cultural elements most visibly impacted by Internet exposure, followed by religion (11.8%) and sports (10.3%). Crucially, responses are distributed across all cultural domains, indicating that Internet-driven cultural change is not limited to a single sphere of life but is pervasive across the sociocultural landscape of Nkanu East.

Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the study's findings in relation to the research questions and existing literature. It is important to note that the survey instrument was designed to measure respondents' perceptions and opinions rather than to establish causal relationships. Accordingly, the language of the findings reflects association rather than causation.

Regarding the association between new sociocultural behaviours and Internet content consumption, the data showed that 60.9% of respondents perceived a high or higher-extent association between their changing sociocultural behaviours and their Internet consumption habits. This finding is consistent with the arguments of Straubhaar and LaRose (2002) and the empirical conclusions of Unwana (2020), Nwaolikpe (2020), and Onoja et al. (2020), all of whom documented Internet-mediated behavioural changes across different Nigerian population groups.

Regarding the extent of Internet exposure, 60.9% of respondents indicated high or higher exposure to Internet contents, directly challenging earlier assertions that the rural infrastructure deficit in Nigeria effectively insulates rural communities from significant Internet influence (Emejulu, 2004; Eze, 2007; Sambe, 2007). The finding aligns with Agba's (2002) characterisation of the Internet as an information revolution that has permeated the globe, and with Macrotrends' (2024) data indicating that approximately 45.4% of Nigeria's population resides in rural areas, where Internet penetration is evidently less limited than previously assumed.

With regard to Internet content preferences, sociocultural and religious movies accounted for the largest share of consumption (50.9%). During interview sessions, respondents confirmed that audio-visual content delivered through smart phones and digitised television, including foreign serials such as Zee World, Star Life, Telemundo, and M-Net, gradually influenced their cultural orientations. This finding is consistent with the media bombardment thesis articulated by Adamu (2006), who documented how continuous exposure to Indian film music transformed Hausa traditional musical culture. The demonstrative, affectively engaging nature of film and video content appears to make it a particularly powerful vehicle of cultural influence.

The dominance of smart mobile phones (45.4%) and digitised television (37.3%) as Internet-access technologies is significant. These devices are personal, portable, and increasingly affordable, making them effective channels for reaching rural populations. Their prevalence in Nkanu East corroborates Agu's (2011) observation that ICTs have evolved from merely functional communication tools to transformative social instruments. Together, these findings suggest that the digital divide between urban and rural Nigeria, while real, is narrower than the infrastructure-deficit literature implies.

The findings on Internet channels demonstrate that television, WhatsApp, and YouTube together account for approximately 68% of content consumption activity. These are platforms that facilitate both passive viewing and active participation, enabling users to both receive and re-share culturally loaded content. This bidirectional quality is particularly relevant to the homogenisation argument: as rural residents share and receive content across social media platforms, cultural norms are transmitted, reinforced, and gradually assimilated.

The distribution of cultural impacts across all domains, spanning politics and news, fashion, religion, and language, confirms the observation of MacBride et al. (1981) that modern media penetrates virtually every dimension of social life. Selected qualitative findings illustrate this breadth. On fashion, one respondent, a housewife of approximately 50 years of age who had never lived outside Nkanu East,

defended her adoption of contemporary Western-influenced dressing styles by invoking the global visibility of such trends: 'This is what trends in this generation. Don't you see people much older than I am, wear worse types than my own, even on international television, which the entire world watches?' This observation reflects the normalising effect of media saturation on cultural boundaries and is consistent with Kraid's (2004) argument that cultural globalisation has increasingly Americanised identities in even the most remote parts of the world.

On religion, respondents reported that their contact with miracles telecast on Internet platforms had accelerated their transition from primordial traditional religion to Christianity. They noted that a hybrid religious culture had emerged, in which traditional religious practices were retained where they did not conflict with Christian doctrine. On politics, respondents indicated that their active participation in the 2019 and 2023 general elections, particularly through online monitoring of vote collation, was facilitated by the Internet. One respondent stated: 'No matter the antics of the government in power, with their hate speech bill, trying to gag the traditional media and the social media commentators, they could not stop us from talking.' These qualitative observations reinforce the quantitative findings and indicate that Internet-driven cultural change in Nkanu East is not a passive or superficial phenomenon.

Summary Of Findings

The following findings emerged from data collected, collated, and analysed in this study:

1. There is a strong perceived association between the new sociocultural behaviours of Nkanu East residents and their consumption of Internet contents (60.9% high to higher extent).
2. Contrary to the infrastructure-deficit argument, Nkanu East residents reported substantial exposure to Internet contents, with 60.9% indicating high or higher exposure.
3. Sociocultural and religious movies constituted the most consumed category of Internet content (50.9%), followed by sports and political content.
4. Smart mobile phones (45.4%) and digitised television (37.3%) were the dominant Internet-access technologies, indicating significant digital penetration even in this remote rural area.
5. WhatsApp/YouTube and television were the most widely used Internet channels.
6. The impact of Internet exposure was distributed across virtually all domains of cultural life, including politics, news, fashion, religion, sports, language, and commerce.

Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence that Internet penetration in rural Nkanu East LGA of Enugu State is more extensive than infrastructure-deficit arguments suggest, and that it is meaningfully associated with observable shifts in residents' sociocultural identities. The findings indicate that primordial cultural values, norms, and practices are increasingly giving way to globally circulated, largely Western-inflected cultural forms, a process facilitated by smart mobile phones, digitised television, and social media platforms such as WhatsApp, YouTube, and Facebook. The evidence suggests that cultural homogenisation in this rural community is neither superficial nor confined to a single domain of life; rather, it pervades politics, religion, fashion, commerce, education, and language.

These findings do not render indigenous culture passive or inevitably doomed to extinction. As this study shows, hybridisation, that is, the co-existence and blending of indigenous and foreign cultural elements, is as common as outright replacement. Nevertheless, the trajectory of change is clear: without deliberate policy and community action, the pace of cultural erosion in communities like Nkanu East is likely to accelerate. The Internet is not merely a medium of information; in rural communities such as this, it is a superhighway of cultural transformation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made to government agencies, cultural institutions, and community stakeholders:

1. Governments at all levels should intensify efforts to protect native sociocultural identities through formal education, with emphasis on indigenous languages, history, and cultural values in the curricula of local schools within vulnerable cultural communities.
2. State and national governments, working through the National Orientation Agency (NOA) and relevant cultural bodies, should mount sustained and localised reorientation campaigns directed at preserving the harmless and valuable cultural identities of the people.
3. Government should encourage and support the use of community radios, local television stations, and digital teleporting platforms to promote and disseminate indigenous values, norms, and traditions in local and native languages and dialects.
4. Internet-savvy community members and cultural advocates should be encouraged to use the same social media platforms, namely WhatsApp, YouTube, and Facebook, that are driving cultural homogenisation to actively document, celebrate, and redistribute indigenous cultural content.
5. Further research is recommended on the mechanisms of cultural hybridisation in rural communities, with particular attention to the role of social media algorithms in amplifying certain categories of cultural content over others.

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